

FLOATECH

D5.3. Report on the LCOE parametrization for AWC and AWM wind turbines

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Background: about the FLOATECH project

The FLOATECH project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union's H2020 programme aiming to increase the technical maturity and the cost competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) energy. This is particularly important because, due to the limitations of available installation sites onshore, offshore wind is becoming crucial to ensure the further growth of the wind energy sector.

The project is implemented by a European consortium of 5 public research institutions with relevant skills in the field of offshore floating wind energy and 3 industrial partners, two of which have been involved in the most recent developments of floating wind systems.

The approach of FLOATECH can be broken down into three actions:

- The development, implementation and validation of a user-friendly and efficient design engineering tool (named QBlade-Ocean) performing simulations of floating offshore wind turbines with an unprecedented combination of aerodynamic and hydrodynamic fidelity. The advanced modelling theories will lead to a reduction of the uncertainties in the design process and an increase of turbine efficiency.
- The development of two innovative control techniques: the Active Wave-based feed-forward Control, combining wave prediction and anticipation of induced platform motion to reduce oscillations and loads, and the Active Wake Mixing, aiming at minimizing wake effects in floating wind farms, leading to a net increase in the annual energy production of the farm.
- The economic analysis of these concepts to demonstrate qualitatively and quantitatively the impact of the developed technologies on the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) of FOW technology.

In addition to the technological and economic impacts, the project is expected to have several impacts at societal, environmental and political levels, such as: public acceptance, due to no noise and visibility issues of FOWT; very low impact on biodiversity and wildlife habitat because no large subsea supporting structures are needed, although, for some specific type of seabed, some environmental effects may be related to the anchoring system; the use of less material and space thanks to an environmentally friendly design; the promotion of the installation of FOW in transitional water depths (30-50 m), as the costs for FOW at those locations will become more competitive compared to the fixed bottom foundations.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
CRF	Capital Recovery Factor
AEP	Annual Energy Production
WP	Work package
AWC	Active Wave Control
AWM	Active Wake Mixing
FF	Feed-forward
DEL	Damage Equivalent Load
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
PPI	Producer Price Index (TPPI indicates the total PPI, comprising domestic and international trading price index)
BOS	Balance of Station

List of symbols

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
DECEX	Decommissioning costs
M_{xyTB}	Combined bending moment at the tower base

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the estimation model for the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) that has been developed in FLOATECH's WP5, based on the studies reported in previous deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. The model here presented has been developed concurrently with the two previous tasks in WP5 for the estimation of the LCOE variations due to the new control technologies developed in the FLOATECH framework. The scope of the activity was the development of a more general tool to evaluate the cost of energy production of an offshore floating turbine. In order to perform the LCOE estimation, the costs and energy production performance, taken into account in the model, have been expressed as a function of three types of parameters:

- turbine and farm configuration and operation parameters: this category of parameters, widely used in other parametric cost models available in literature, comprises some geometrical and performance parameters such as
 - turbine rotor diameter, tower height, platform size, mooring characteristics;
 - wind farm layout (influencing the wake interactions and treated assuming a simplified farm geometry);
- environmental parameters:
 - site water depth;
 - met-ocean conditions;
- loading conditions: differently from other parametric models, in this work a preliminary load estimation has been considered. The evaluation of loading conditions has been carried out mainly using the results of the FOWT simulation code QBlade, which has been one of the main topics in the development of the FLOATECH project. The need for such load estimation is related to the objective of estimating the effect of the new control technologies introduced in FLOATECH, which may affect the overall FOWT response, influencing both performance and loads. The effect of possible load variations may, in turn, modify the expected component costs after the change in the adopted control technique, if a revision of the component sizing is required to preserve the same structural safety level as in the initial design. In this work, however, the effects of load variation are accounted for only in a preliminary way: once a required modification of component sizing has been estimated, the effect of such variation on the FOWT response and load levels should be estimated as well, in an iterative process, which is outside the scope of the preliminary cost-oriented study at which this analysis is aimed.

While deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 have shown the estimation of the effects on the component sizing of turbine design and control, the present document focuses specifically on a more detailed description of the economic cost modelling.

2 INTRODUCTION

The notion of LCOE is widely used in the field of the economic assessment of energy related projects and it has been applied also to the analysis of renewable energy applications. It accounts for both the costs and performance of an energy production system. The case of floating wind turbines is characterized by several specific technical issues, currently still under investigation and not yet fully addressed. This situation results, generally, in a higher level of the overall plant cost, which reduces the economic effectiveness of offshore projects compared to more mature technologies, such as, for example, onshore wind plants or bottom fixed offshore installations. Nonetheless, strong interest has been shown by possible investors in the exploitation of the significant potential resources available in the deep-sea offshore environment, also driven by national and international policy interventions and regulations for the control of pollutant emissions. This trend is well represented by the continuous increase of offshore installed wind power during the last years in Europe and around the world (mainly bottom fixed but recently also with floating plant installations) [1] [2]; a reduction in the growth trend has been observed, however, in recent times, probably due to the conjunctural economic and political situations.

The path towards an efficient and affordable design of floating wind turbines is still in progress, as testified by the currently high LCOE. Such parameter will be used in this study as the major techno-economic indicator for the assessment of offshore wind energy plants. Typical LCOE values reported in literature for different installations (expressed in units of €/MWh) show a significant dispersion, due to different estimation methods and hypotheses used in the evaluation process as well as to the differences in the available wind resource for the considered installation sites [3]. According to a 2022 study [4], a variation of the predicted LCOE value ranging in the interval 93.6 €/MWh – 183.9 €/MWh can be observed in the case of a spar buoy platform configuration, as retrieved from several literature references (values have been converted from Pounds to Euros at the current exchange rate, assumed equal to 1.16€/£). Other sources (for example [5]) report an even wider range of variation, with an extreme value of about 287 €/MWh. A wide uncertainty range can be observed in LCOE estimation and larger intervals can be expected if the variations of some relevant financial parameters (such as inflation and cost of capital) are also taken into account. Such values are quite larger compared to the ones observed for fixed-bottom applications, which are around 80 €/MWh and to further lower LCOE values of about 40 €/MWh for onshore wind (by 2020, according to GWEC [6]).

The developed model has been tailored on the configuration considered in this work, a spar-buoy type platform, based on the ECN SoftWind model developed by Ecole centrale de Nantes; this model has been used throughout the FLOATECH project for the analyses carried out in other work packages and, particularly, for the development of the investigated control strategies. The main configuration parameters of the SoftWind model have been used for cost estimation and a corresponding QBlade model has been used for the simulations providing load estimation. The cost model, although tested only for the above indicated case, may be, in principle, extended to different specific designs, by replacing the proper configuration data (geometry and performance parameters) and the related simulation results (component loads).

3 GENERAL DEFINITIONS AND ASSUMPTIONS

In this study, the following expression has been used for LCOE estimation:

$$LCOE = \frac{CAPEX \times CRF + OPEX + DECEX \times \frac{i}{(1+i)^t - 1}}{AEP} \quad (1)$$

where *CAPEX*, measured in €, indicates the capital expenditures, *OPEX* represents the annual operating costs, measured in €/year, *DECEX*, in €, is referred to the decommissioning costs, *AEP* is the annual energy production, measured in MWh/year and the factor *i* is a *discount rate* assumed to estimate the present value of future costs and energy production at the start time of the project. The estimate of the discount rate has been based on available literature data. More details on cost decomposition are given later in sect. 6.1. The information reported in this section have been treated also in deliverable D5.1 and are briefly recalled here for completeness. The expression above introduces the *Capital Recovery Factor (CRF)* estimated through the following relation:

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1} \quad (2)$$

where *t* is the total duration of the project. The total time of the project, *t*, is considered equal to 20 years. However, the project lifetime is a parameter of the model and can be modified to consider different possible values in the expected plant operational life. A value of the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) equal to 11.5% has been used as an estimate of the discount rate in the present study, based on literature data. Details on the assumed value are indicated in deliverable D5.1 [7].

4 ASSUMED FLOATING TURBINE CONFIGURATION

The SoftWind configuration has been considered in this study for the development of the LCOE calculation model. The assumed configuration has been developed at Ecole Centrale de Nantes (ECN) and has undergone an extensive series of experimental test campaigns; moreover, this design solution has also been already used for the analyses performed in FLOATECH WP2. In any case, some modifications to the original SoftWind configuration have been made. The following assumptions on the system model have been considered:

- rotor and nacelle from DTU 10MW RWT have been considered;
- the tower from OO-Star project has been considered, consistently with the assumptions of WP2;
- the SoftWind platform studied at ECN has been considered (with a modification of the mooring line system adopted in the case of AWM control aiming at improving the effectiveness of the control strategy, as described in [8]).

The geometry of the overall system is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Softwind model.

The platform has a spar buoy configuration with a mooring system composed of a set of three mooring lines connected to the platform by a system of delta connected bridles.

The rotor geometry is described in more details in [9]. Two control systems are considered in the analysis: the baseline control is a standard pitch control for power limitation similar to the one already used in WP2 simulations [10], while the modified control will implement the Active Wave Control (AWC) and Active Wave Mixing (AWM) control techniques, developed in previous work packages and analysed in task 5.1 and 5.2, respectively. These control techniques use specifically developed blade pitch control algorithms to reach different objectives: the AWC control aims at improving the overall motion response of the floating system to the disturbances generated by the incoming waves [7] [11], while the AWM control is oriented to improve the wake recovery behind the rotor by promoting wake mixing [8] [12].

5 METHODOLOGY

5.1 GENERAL APPROACH

In order to estimate the LCOE level for a FOWT, a cost model is needed for both capital and operational costs. This part of the work is essentially shared with the complementary study related to the two control strategies investigated in WP5 (AWC and AWM), introduced in D5.1 and D5.2 [8] [7].

The first part of the work is related to the definition of a procedure to estimate the cost contribution to LCOE as a function of the main configuration parameters, defining a cost model. Regarding the estimation of capital costs, a typical approach is based on a bottom-up procedure, which decomposes the total capital expenditures in several contributions associated to the main components of a FOWT, as described for example in [13], [14], [15]. Typically, the models reported in literature are related to the overall size and dimensions of the considered components (such as the rotor diameter, tower height or other geometric features of interest) or to some performance parameters (such as the turbine rated power). This approach is particularly useful in preliminary cost estimations and scaling studies, but, in the specific case considered in the present work, it has some difficulties in taking into account the possible effects of a

change in the control strategy, which directly affects the overall FOWT response and loadings but is only indirectly related to the geometrical parameters considered by the aforementioned cost models. The methodology adopted to evaluate the LCOE variation induced by the AWC control strategy needs, thus, to pursue a slightly different approach to take into account the possible effects of a change in the control strategy. Specifically, for some components of the FOWT, which are considered more significantly affected by the choice of the control technique, the following scheme is applied:

- 1) a baseline configuration is defined, with a given subset of the design parameters values (such as local thickness of structural elements or other geometrical features influencing the component load bearing capacity);
- 2) a simplified design procedure is set up in order to relate the chosen design parameters to a set of main loads acting on the considered components;
- 3) a simulation-based approach is used to estimate:
 - a. the main loading parameters for the baseline case;
 - b. the same set of loadings for a modified configuration with the control technique implemented;
- 4) the simplified design procedure from point 2) is used to estimate the design parameters for both the baseline configuration and the configuration with the control technique;
- 5) the variation of the component costs is estimated based on the estimated variation of the considered design parameter values.

The components for which this procedure is applied are indicated in the following list:

- rotor blades;
- tower;
- platform;
- mooring lines.

The other costs are estimated from traditional cost models from the literature, mainly based on [14] [16] [17].

Some details on the evaluation of the simplified design parameter choice for the considered components are reported in deliverable D5.1 [7].

It is important to note that the design parameters' choice here presented is far from being a detailed and complete design procedure and has only the purpose to give an initial estimate of the possible trends in cost variation induced by the considered control technique. A detailed design, which is outside the scope of the present cost estimation analysis, would require, on one hand to consider a larger set of operating and environmental conditions to fully comply with standard requirements, and, on the other hand, would probably need an iterative approach (changing the design parameters may alter FOWT response, thereby changing, in turn, also component loadings). The simplified design procedure is shared between the cases studied in the deliverables D5.2 and D5.3.

5.2 SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE DEFINITION OF THE COST MODEL

The basic cost model developed in this work follows a general approach used in other similar studies, based on a decomposition of the overall FOWT unit in a set of subcomponents. For each component a relation between some geometrical parameters and its cost is assumed, generally based on a regression analysis applied to data from similar projects. Examples of such approach are widely diffused in the literature on the techno-economic evaluation of wind energy projects [3] [14] [17] [18]. Details on the assumed expressions for cost estimation are given in the next sections. Such models, purely based on regressions, generally rely only on geometrical and performance parameters (e.g., rotor radius, tower height, rated power, etc.). Thus, for the estimation of the effect of load variations related to a change in control strategy, the procedure outlined in the previous section has been here used, taking into account a wider range of configuration parameters, including the chosen control type. This approach has, however, some limitations:

- the developed cost model is intended to be used in preliminary stages of the projects, for the evaluation of the effectiveness of a design choice. Thus, in general, only a limited amount of data is available like, for example, a limited number of simulation results. In this study, this was particularly true for the case of the wake mixing technology, for which only results for normal operation were available; also for the AWC case, although a larger number of simulations were available, covering a wider operation range, the simulation set was, however, derived from a subset of the whole standard design load cases;
- moreover, the analyses used for the estimation of the variation of the component costs are extremely simplified, according to the general approach of the work; this simplification may however affect the results. This assumption and the previous one will require a check of the results with further analyses along the development of the project, whenever a larger amount of data will be gathered;
- the model requires a number of results from simulations related to the loading and energy production characteristics of the FOWT or, at least, a preliminary estimation of such data. Thus, contrary to the purely regression-based approaches, this procedure needs a more detailed definition and knowledge of the FOWT configuration, which are not easily available in the preliminary project stages (where the model is supposed to be more effectively used). This situation has been observed also in this work, as already pointed out in a previous observation. At least an initial configuration design is needed to proceed with the proposed approach; however, once a tentative configuration has been chosen, some preliminary analyses can be performed with a relatively limited amount of simulation data, allowing an estimation of the LCOE variation, as described in D5.1 and D5.2. As already indicated above, the accuracy of the model may be tested and improved along the project, as soon as a greater amount of data has been gathered;
- the validity of the results is also partly limited by the choice of the components costs considered in the analysis. In the current analysis, the components deemed to be most affected by a control variation have been considered; however, other components have not been considered. In particular, in the case of AWC, the cost of the system itself, still in an experimental phase, has not

been taken into account, while, in both considered cases of control variation, the effects on the pitch system (pitch bearing and actuators) were not taken into account in the design variation procedure. The cost estimation of such components has been treated with the use of expressions found in literature. This choice is based on two considerations: on the one hand, there is a very small amount of data publicly available on the behaviour of pitch system (particularly with respect to the fatigue data) and this lack of data prevents the use of the design revision approach; on the other hand, some discussions with some actors in wind industry suggested a relatively limited impact of such components on the overall FOWT costs.

Despite the highlighted limitations, the developed cost model, which shares the basic structure with already proved and diffused models available in literature, has been deemed adequate for the LCOE evaluation at a preliminary design stage.

In the next sections, further details on the cost model and on the energy production estimation are given.

6 ASSUMPTIONS FOR THE DEFINITION OF THE COST MODEL

6.1 BASIC COMPONENT COST MODELLING

The cost of a floating wind turbine is decomposed in several items, as described in the schematic view shown in Fig. 2. Such items contribute to the overall cost considered in the expression of the LCOE, as reported in sect. 3.

Figure 2. Cost item decomposition in the assumed model.

As briefly mentioned in sect. 3, CAPEX (*CAPital EXpenditure*) costs, which are generally defined for a project as the investments used to upgrade or obtain physical assets in order to create a future benefit [19], typically represent the main contribution to the overall cost of the FOWT and covers all costs incurred before the start of the commercial operation, including the costs of the components and the installation

procedures. The CAPEX costs include also an item related to the project development which accounts for the preliminary studies and the engineering activities involved in the initial stages of the project.

OPEX (OPERational EXPenditure) costs are related to the costs incurred, after the start of the facility operation and prior to the decommissioning, to ensure the continuous operation of the plant, including the maintenance costs. OPEX can generally be divided into a fixed part and a variable part. The fixed part generally includes administration, insurance, grid access fees, scheduled maintenance, related to operational costs; while the variable part is related to unscheduled maintenance interventions, not covered by fixed contracts, and corrective maintenance costs.

Finally, the DECEX costs are related to the costs sustained in the last part of the project for the plant removal and the possible restoration of the installation site.

A parametric model of the main cost items will be here introduced accounting for basic component costs and for the cost of installations. Such model will provide a baseline value for the cost estimation, which will be varied, accounting for the variation of the control system according to the procedure outlined in sect. 5 and in the deliverables D5.1 and 5.2.

In this section, based on literature data, the expressions used for the basic cost estimation will be presented. The main sources of data for the assumed regression-based cost expressions are the already cited works by NREL [14] [16], together with other studies reported in [3] [18].

A set of key turbine descriptors is assumed to define the characteristics of the model that influence component costs. Table 1 summarizes the considered parameters and the values assumed in the analysis.

Table 1. Main turbine configuration descriptors considered in the model.

MAIN CONFIGURATION INPUTS		
Rotor		
R (m)	89.2	Rotor Radius
P_{rated} (kW)	10000	Rated power
H (m)	116	Hub height
Mooring		
Nominal diameter (mm)	165	
Minimum breaking load (kN)	18699	
Number of lines	3	
Chain Length (m)	732.0	Baseline
	732.0	Modified
Site		
w_d (m)	200	Water depth

Besides this configuration-related data, the cost estimation process needs some financial assumptions, indicated in the Table 2.

Table 2. Financial inputs.

i	11.50%	<i>discount rate</i>
n (year)	20	<i>project duration</i>
year	2022	<i>(used for price scaling with respect to the reference period of the available data)</i>

The discount rate is directly used in the expression for the LCOE estimation (reported in sect. 3). It has been estimated based on literature data [20], with a correction for inflation level (as indicated in sect. 3). The project duration has also a direct effect on the estimation of LCOE. The last financial input is associated to the choice of the year considered for the cost estimation, which is related to the general variation of prices with time, as accounted for by inflation related indexes, such as the Producer Price Index and the Consumer Price Index. The costs estimated using the assumed expressions are, in fact, generally defined in terms of currency values at a given reference time. Thus, a correction is applied to the estimated costs, based on the inflation index, in order to evaluate the costs at a specific time. The data considered to account for the variation of prices with time are shown in the next sections for the different type of materials used in component construction.

The expressions used for cost estimation are generally based on similar structures. Most of the expressions are proportional to the mass of the component, which in turn is related to component specific geometrical characteristics.

In some cases, the final cost of some components (as, for example, it has been assumed in this study for the platform construction) will be estimated accounting for a manufacturing complexity factor, which will be accounted for directly in the cost per unit mass of the component material (more details are given in the section dedicated to the platform).

Finally, for the components indicated in sect. 5.1, a further cost modification factor is applied in order to account for the load variation associated to the change in the applied control technique, as described in [7].

6.2 COST ESTIMATION FOR THE MAIN TURBINE COMPONENTS

This section indicates the expressions used for the estimation of the baseline main component costs, based on typical statistical relationships available in literature. A parametric model has been derived from publicly available market information and literature data.

6.2.1 Turbine steel components

For the steel components comprised in the turbine assembly, the following expression has been used for the evaluation of the baseline turbine cost items.

Table 3. Expressions for baseline costs in € of main turbine steel and nacelle components (based on [16]).

Component	Cost expression	
Nacelle		
Hub cost	$= 4.25 \times [0.954 \times (0.1452 * R^{2.9158}) + 5680.3] \times 1.79$	(3)
Pitch system cost (three blades)	$= 2.28 \times [0.2106 \times (2R)^{2.6578}] \times 1.56$	(4)
Nose cone cost	$= 5.57 \times (18.5 \times (2R) - 520.5) \times 1.39$	(5)
Low speed shaft cost	$= 0.01 \times (2R)^{2.887} \times 1.79$	(6)
Mainframe cost	$= 303.96 \times (2R)^{1.067} \times 1.79$	(7)
Bearing cost	$= 2 \times 17.6 \times \left(2R \frac{8}{600} - 0.033\right) \times 0.0092 \times (2R)^{2.5} \times 1.49$	(8)
Gearbox cost	$= 16.45 \times (P_{rated_{kW}})^{1.249} \times 1.49$	(9)
Brake, coupling costs	$= (1.9894 \times (P_{rated_{kW}}) - 0.1141) \times 1.49$	(10)
Generator cost	$= (P_{rated_{kW}}) \times 65 \times 1.49$	(11)
Variable speed electronics cost	$= P_{rated_{kW}} \times 79 \times 0.97$	(12)
Yaw drive and bearing cost	$= 2 \times [0.0339 \times (2R)^{2.964}] \times 1.49$	(13)
Nacelle cover cost	$= [11.537 \times P_{rated_{kW}} + 3849.7] \times 1.49$	(14)
Electrical connections	$= 40 \times P_{rated_{kW}} \times 0.97$	(15)
Control, safety system, condition monitoring cost	$= 55000 \times 0.97$	(16)

In the above reported expressions, R denotes the rotor radius (in m) and the machine power rating, P_{rated} , is expressed in kW.

The turbine cost, $C_{Turbine}$, is expressed as the sum of the above reported components.

The tower cost is also estimated as a function of geometrical parameters (rotor swept area, S_{Rotor} (in m²) and hub height, H_{hub} , (in m)), as indicated below.

Table 4. Tower cost in € (based on [16]).

Tower		
Tower cost	$C_{Tower} = 1.25 \times (0.3973 \times S_{Rotor} \times H_{hub} - 1414) \times 1.79$	(17)

An additional cost item is added to the above indicated costs in order to account for marine specific requirements (such as special protections or treatment).

Table 5. Marinization cost in € (based on [16]).

Marinization		
Marinization cost	$0.135 \times (C_{Turbine} + C_{Tower})$	(18)

6.2.2 Composite material components

Similar reasoning will be used also for components in non-metallic materials, such as the fibre reinforced composites used in blade construction. In the construction of a wind turbine blade, several different materials are used with different costs, and complex manufacturing operations are required. Moreover, additional costs have to be considered, in general, to account for the cost of moulds and other related tools and equipment (a very detailed cost model for the blade can be found in [21] only, beyond the scope of this work and the availability of data in a preliminary design phase). The cost model of the blade has a more complex nature, involving a more complex structure; some models, as in [16], assume a given combination of the different blade components (fiberglass fabric, adhesives, fastener and other metallic parts, foam components). The indicated reference gives an expression for the cost, C_{blade} , and the mass, m_{blade} , of a blade as a function of the blade radius (measured from the rotor axis) [16]:

$$C_{blade} = \frac{(0.4019 \times R^3 - 955.24) + 2.7445 \times R^{2.5025}}{1 - 0.28} \quad (19)$$

$$m_{blade} = 0.083 \times R^{2.9158} \quad (20)$$

Note that the first term at the numerator of eq. (19) is related to the material cost, while the second term is related to the labour cost.

For a given radius, the cost per unit mass can be established by considering the ratio of the above expressions. In the present work the radius of the blade will be assumed constant (equal to the radius of the DTU 10MW RWT, $R=89.2$ m). Thus, the cost per unit mass of the blade, c_{blade} , estimated using the above indicated expression for the mass, is reported below for reference only:

$$c_{blade_{2002}} = 17.33 \text{ €/kg} \quad (21)$$

The above indicated values are related to the reference period and currency used in the original cost NREL model (referred to 2002 dollars). To account for possible variations of the producer price index and of the cost of labour from the reference year of the assumed cost model, an increase factor is considered, leading to the following value for the assumed current blade cost to mass ratio:

$$c_{blade_{2022}} = 24.80 \text{ €/kg} \quad (22)$$

The correction for the production cost is based on the historical trends of material cost and inflation, described later in the sect. 6.5. In this study, a correction factor has been applied to the blade cost to estimate the current cost level (by 2022) from the original model, referred to 2002 cost data. Different correction factors were applied for the material cost component and for the labour cost (in eq. (19)). The correction factor for the materials in the blade (here assumed equal to about 1.36) was estimated as the ratio of the average producer price indexes for the two considered time periods. Using a similar approach, the labour cost correction factor (here assumed equal to 1.56) was estimated as the ratio of consumer price indexes for the two considered time periods. The consumer price index is generally different from the producer price index and is related to market price for final user and, in turn, this parameter is related to the general inflation index; in this study the consumer price index has been considered as more directly related to the labour cost variations, at least as a first approximation, and therefore it has been used to scale the labour component of the cost.

Moreover, the value of the blade mass, used to estimate the cost per unit mass, has been corrected with respect to the value of the original model (eq. (20)) to match the known effective weight of the considered blade.

6.3 BALANCE OF STATION COSTS

In the balance of station (or balance of plant) costs, all the costs other than the direct turbine costs are included, comprising the items indicated in the following table [14].

Table 6. List of the items considered for the BOS cost estimation.

<i>Balance of Station cost items</i>
Substructure
Transport and installation
Mooring system
Electrical interconnection
Other costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contingency • Insurance • Project development

Details on the estimation of each considered item are given in the next subsections.

6.3.1 Substructure

For the estimation of the cost of the platform, an approach based on the estimation of the required platform mass has been assumed. The model, based on [14], estimates the mass of the platform as a function of performance parameters (rated power) and of the site characteristics (water depth).

The overall production cost of a component is largely influenced also by the cost of labour besides the raw material cost. This variable is more difficult to estimate in a simplistic approach. The approach used in this work assumes that the cost of a component can be expressed as a function of its mass, as assumed in other works (for example, [13] or [14]). In order to account for the manufacturing process, a multiplicative factor (sometimes defined as *complexity factor*) is often considered, as described, for example, in [19] or [22]. Different works use different coefficient values to account for the cost of manufacturing process. For a spar buoy type configuration, some of the cited references give a value of the complexity factor equal to approximately 120%; this value is, however, significantly dependent on the available technological manufacturing solutions and facilities and thus it is not easy to make a general estimate. The assumed value has to be considered only in the perspective of an initial estimation with the purpose of comparing different technological solutions (in our case, the innovative control techniques). However, the manufacturing of the platform involves complex and expensive activities, characteristic of large marine constructions. In this work, instead of using a single complexity factor, different unit costs per material mass, derived from literature, have been used for the different parts of the platform; thus, the complexity factor is accounted for directly in the unit cost of each part of the substructure, with the aim of developing a more detailed description of the cost contributions from the different substructure elements. The assumed unit costs are specifically related to the considered spar buoy platform configuration. The overall mass of the spar buoy structure is divided in several subcomponents: the stiffened column (the longer cylindrical part below the transition piece connected to the tower); the tapered column (the part of the spar comprising also a tapered transition zone from the lower stiffened column to the upper connection to the tower); the outfitting (comprising all the accessory parts); the fixed ballast. According to [14], the unit costs indicated in the Table 7 have been applied to the different platform elements:

Table 7. Cost of different platform parts
(Costs are converted from USD values reported in [14]).

Component	Cost (€/t)
Stiffened Column	3057.6
Tapered Column	4135.6
Outfitting	7105.0
Fixed Ballast	147.0

The above indicated values will be multiplied by the mass of the corresponding components or parts to estimate the contribution to the total cost. The mass of each part is estimated for the baseline case starting from the known geometrical characteristics of the platform. The same reference provides expressions for the expected mass of the spar elements, as shown in the Table 8.

Table 8. Mass of different platform parts (from expressions reported in [14]).

Component	Mass (kg)	
Stiffened Column	$(535.93 + 17.664 (P_{rated_{MW}})^2 + 0.02328 \times w_d \times \ln(w_d)) \times 1.7$	(23)
Tapered Column	$(125.81 \ln(P_{rated_{MW}}) + 58.712) \times 2.4$	(24)
Outfitting	$\exp(3.58 + 0.196 * (P_{rated_{MW}})^{0.5} \times \ln(P_{rated_{MW}}) + 0.00001 * w_d * \ln(w_d))$	(25)
Fixed Ballast	$(-16.536 \times (P_{rated_{MW}})^2 + 1261.8 \times P_{rated_{MW}} - 1554.6) \times 1.5$	(26)

In the above expressions the rated power is expressed in MW and w_d indicates the water depth.

It has to be noted that the original values from reference [14] have been corrected, using the multiplying coefficients indicated in the above table, to match the mass values assumed in the simulation models.

6.3.2 Transport and installation

The costs of transportation to the site and installation procedures are also considered as parts of the balance of station cost. These items have a slightly more complex expression, which corresponds to the complexity of the operations to be performed prior and during the installation phases. This cost, moreover, is dependent on the type of the chosen installation procedure. According to [17], multiple items have to be considered in the estimation of the transport and installation costs, as indicated in Table 9. Moreover, the assumed expressions for the transport cost items depend on several different parameters, related to the power performance of the turbine and to the location of the installation site.

Table 9. Variables affecting the cost of installation and transport.

Transport and installation cost components	Description
C_t	Turbine installation cost
C_s	Substructure installation cost
C_{ps}	Port and staging cost
Influencing variables	
D_p	Distance from staging port to project site
D_a	Distance from staging port to inshore assembly area
D_{as}	Distance from inshore assembly area to project site
<i>Rated power</i>	

As indicated before, this type of cost item is related to the considered installation procedure. In this case, it is assumed that there is a previous phase of mounting (in an intermediate inshore site) and then a transport to the final deployment site. Thus, the expression takes into account different distance parameters (from the port to the assembly area, from the port to the final installation site, from the assembly area to the installation site). Such distances affect the overall final cost through their effect on some operative parameters (such as the duration of the transport operations, the cost of personnel and vessels, etc.).

The estimation proposed in [17] considers an interpolation between the available cost data for three different installations with different rated powers (from 3 to 10 MW). The cost contributions for the different rated powers considered in this approach are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Expressions for the transport and installation costs in €.

Rated power	Transport and Installation costs	
3 MW	$C_s = \frac{70146438 + 87703 \times D_a + 44830 \times D_p}{200} \times 1.44$ $C_t = \frac{1.399e8 + 19972 \times D_a + 270417 \times D_p}{200} \times 1.44$ $C_{ps} = \frac{25237609 + 23896 \times D_a + 21667 \times D_{as}}{200} \times 1.44$	(27)
6 MW	$C_s = \frac{83062187 + 88643 \times D_a + 65900 \times D_p}{100} \times 1.44$ $C_t = \frac{149900000 + 41598 \times D_a + 245417 \times D_{as}}{100} \times 1.44$ $C_{ps} = \frac{26525627 + 25367 \times D_a + 21667 \times D_{as}}{100} \times 1.44$	(28)
10 MW	$C_s = \frac{94577688 + 90048 \times D_a + 85033 \times D_p}{60} \times 1.44$ $C_t = \frac{1.75e8 + 73499 \times D_a + 290417 \times D_{as}}{60} \times 1.44$ $C_{ps} = \frac{28101577 + 27188 \times D_a + 21667 \times D_{as}}{60} \times 1.44$	(29)

The model is parametrized in terms of the operation related distances, besides other basic configuration parameters already introduced, such as the rated power. For the present analysis, the values indicated in Table 11 are used.

Table 11. Assumed parameter values for the transport and installation cost evaluation.

Distance from staging port to project site	D_p (km)	=	42
Distance from staging port to inshore assembly area	D_a (km)	=	2
Distance from inshore assembly area to project site	D_{as} (km)	=	40

As already stated, the rated power of the turbine is equal to 10 MW (other data are reported here for completeness).

6.3.3 Mooring system

For the cost of mooring chains and anchors, the following relations have been used, according to [23]:

$$\text{Chain cost} = (0.0591 \times MBL - 89.69) \times L \quad (30)$$

$$\text{Anchor cost} = 10.198 \times MBL \quad (31)$$

where L is the length of the mooring chain and MBL indicates the minimum breaking load of the chain, which is related to the chain nominal section diameter, d_c . Moreover, some standards give an expression that relates the MBL and d_c [24].

6.3.4 Electrical connections

The electrical interconnection cost is estimated using the following expression:

$$\text{Electrical connection cost} = (753.01 D_p + 39038) \quad (32)$$

as a function of the distance to the connection point, here assumed equal to the distance from the staging port, D_p (in km). These cost item refers to the export cable to the onshore connection.

When considering a farm installation, also the cost of array cables and of the electrical infrastructure have to be considered. In this study, a simplified expression for the total length of the connection cables between the FOWT units in a farm has been considered, assuming a simple square layout; according to [15], the following expression has been used to estimate the total cable length, L_C

$$L_C = s D_t (N_t - 1) \quad (33)$$

where the connection length is expressed as a function of the non-dimensional turbine distance, s , defined as the ratio of the turbine distance to the turbine rotor diameter, of the rotor diameter D_t , and of the number of installed units. The cost of the internal array cables, C_{cables} is then expressed assuming a cost of the cable per unit length, C_C :

$$C_{cables} = C_C \times L_C \quad (34)$$

where, according to [15], the cable unit cost can be assumed equal to $C_C = 675 \text{ €/m}$.

It must be noted that other electrical components, particularly the electrical hub, have not been considered in this preliminary estimation model.

6.3.5 Other Balance of System cost items

Other cost items have to be considered in order to account for the possible adjustment interventions to the project for issues not previously considered, indicated as contingency costs. Specifically, an expression for the contingency is assumed as a given percentage of the total CAPEX costs.

Moreover, the costs of project development are also considered in the overall BOS costs.

The assumed additional costs are indicated in the Table 12.

Table 12. Additional cost in € (based on [16]).

Contingency	$0.10 \times CAPEX$	(35)
Insurance	$38 \times [P_{rated_{kW}}] \times 1.31$	(36)
Project development	$1.5E9 \times [P_{rated_{kW}}] \times 1.12$	(37)

6.4 OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE AND DECOMMISSIONING COSTS

6.4.1 Operation and maintenance costs

OPEX are expressed, according to [3], as a function of the distance from staging port to project site, D_p (in km), and of the rated power (in kW), using the following expression:

$$OPEX = (138000 + 40 \times (D_p - 200)) \times (rated\ power(kW))/1000 \quad (38)$$

6.4.2 Decommissioning

According to [3], the decommissioning costs, can be expressed as a percentage of the installation costs. Table 13 shows the assumed fraction of the installation costs, different for each component involved in the decommissioning phase.

Table 13. Decommissioning cost as a percentage of the installation cost [3], for different components.

Wind turbine	70%
Subsea cables	10%
Mooring system	90%

It has to be noted that, in the current study, the decommissioning cost of the substation has been neglected and that the decommissioning cost for the cables and mooring system have been estimated based on the related CAPEX values rather than on the installation costs, as per lack of detailed data.

It should be also pointed out that different models provide significantly different values for the decommissioning costs. For example, the original NREL model [16] suggests a simple expression of the DECEX costs equal to a 3% fraction of the total CAPEX, yielding a significantly lower value with respect to the results of the assumed model. Considering the uncertainty about the effective decommissioning costs, the more conservative estimation has been assumed in this work.

6.5 OTHER ASSUMPTIONS AND COST CONTRIBUTIONS

6.5.1 Material cost assumptions

Regarding the cost of steel components, the price of steel has undergone considerable fluctuation in a period close to the time of writing. A set of historic data available in the public domain is reported in Figure 3 based on the BCE database on steel import price in the Euro area.

Figure 3. Normalized steel price index since 2005. (Source BCE, 2023, steel import price).

Considering a 2015 price of about 392 €/ton (estimated as an average of rebar and plate raw materials) [25], the projection for the average steel price variation in the recent years is reported in Figure 4. Considering the last period of the overall trend around year 2022, a peak value of the raw material cost equal to about 700 €/ton can be estimated. For conservativeness and to account for possible market uncertainty, a value of $c_{steel, raw} = 1,000$ €/ton has been assumed for the base cost of steel raw material.

Figure 4. Estimated steel price since 2005. (Source BCE, 2023, for steel import price).

6.5.2 Economic and Financial assumptions

As described in previous sections, several models have been considered for the estimation of the component costs. A methodological concern about the application of the above-mentioned models is related to the necessity of a conversion procedure of the estimated costs to current economical values. The cost models generally estimate cost values referred to a specific year (accounting for the general price levels and cost of labour in a chosen time period). In order to get results related to a different time period, a conversion procedure has to be applied. Specifically, in order to provide projections referring to the current economic conditions, the Producer Price Index (*PPI*) has been considered. This parameter is an indicator of the development over time of transaction prices; it, generally, includes both the domestic and international trading prices, defining the Total Producer Price Index (indicated as *TPPI*).

The procedure for cost value conversion requires two steps:

- currency conversion step: some data are related to different markets in a given time period (generally a specific year); in order to retrieve results expressed in euro currency values, a simple currency conversion factor has been applied:

$$\text{€}^{t_{ref}} = \frac{C^{t_{ref}}}{K_{X/\text{€}}^{t_{ref}}} \quad (39)$$

where $C^{t_{ref}}$ represents the economic value at the reference year, t_{ref} , to be converted from a given currency to the value $\text{€}^{t_{ref}}$ in euros and $K_{X/\text{€}}^{t_{ref}}$ is the currency conversion factor for the specified year; the currency conversion factor for year 2002 (used in [16]) has been assumed equal to

$$K_{\$/\text{€}}^{2002} = (\$/\text{€})^{2002} = 0.98 \text{ \$/€} \quad (40)$$

while the Pounds to Euro conversion for 2017 (used in [18]) has been equal to

$$K_{\text{€}/\text{€}}^{2017} = 0.89 \text{ €}/\text{€}; \quad (41)$$

- inflation correction step: all cost values are converted to present values using the *TPPI* index ratio between the current time, $TPPI^t$, and the reference time index value, $TPPI^{t_{ref}}$:

$$\text{€}^t = \text{€}^{t_{ref}} \frac{TPPI^t}{TPPI^{t_{ref}}} \quad (42)$$

For the cost of labour, on the other hand, a scaling factor proportional to the general inflation index is used. This parameter, used to convert the costs of labour-intensive components, is strictly related to the specific market considered and, as the other economic parameter cited in this section, will be estimated according to data provided in the public domain.

In some cases, besides of the Producer Price Index, also the Consumer Price Index (CPI) has been used in the scaling process. This indicator is related to the general variation of the prices of goods and services acquired by households and has been assumed approximately related to the cost of labour. In particular, in the case of the blades (sect. 6.2.2), beside the material cost variations, which have been scaled using the TPPI indicator, also a contribution due to the labour cost has been considered, which has been scaled using the CPI indicator.

Data for the reported indicators can be retrieved from [26]. This approach for the scaling of economic values is similar to the methodology used in [27].

The components for which this correction procedure has been used are summarized in Table 14, together with the considered scaling factors.

Table 14. Component costs estimated through regression model and escalation factors.

Component	Escalation factor
Hub	TPPI
Blade	TPPI and CPI
Pitch mechanism and bearings	TPPI
Low speed shaft	TPPI
Bearings	TPPI
Gearbox	TPPI
Mechanical brake, high-speed coupling,	TPPI
Generator	TPPI
Variable-speed electronics	TPPI
Yaw drive and bearing	TPPI
Main frame	TPPI
Electrical connections	TPPI
Hydraulic system	TPPI
Nacelle cover	TPPI
Control, safety system	TPPI
Electrical interconnection	TPPI

7 ANNUAL ENERGY PRODUCTION

To complete the process of LCOE evaluation, an estimation of the annual energy production is also needed. The information needed for such estimation are briefly presented below. In this study, the effects of wake interactions have also been accounted for, as they are necessary to extend the estimation of energy production from a single floating wind turbine to a floating wind farm (particularly for the case of the wake mixing control, which is aiming to improve the wake recovery). Thus, some assumptions were made both on wake modelling and on the wind farm geometry, as also briefly described here. These data have already been described in the previous deliverable D5.1 and D5.2, where they have been used in the LCOE estimation process for each of the considered control technologies and are reported here for completeness and to improve the readability of the document.

7.1 ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION MODELING

The impact of climate characteristics on energy production performance of a single turbine and of a farm is of primary importance. In this study, for simplicity, the climate of a given offshore site has been chosen, assuming it could be representative of a larger set of sites of possible interest for the installation of floating wind farms. The chosen site is the same used for the analyses performed in WP2 [10] [28]. The considered location, is placed west of the Scottish isle of Barra, with an approximate depth of 200 m. For this site a long-term time series of met-ocean data were available in the public environmental database ERA5 [29]. The main reasons behind the choice of this specific site can be found in two points: on the one hand, as already indicated, this choice is consistent with data previously used in this and other FOWT related projects [30]; on the other hand, this site is characterized by relatively harsh climatic conditions, which allows to highlight possible severe loading combinations.

From the considered data, a joint distribution of wind speed and direction has been obtained and provided as input to the model for the estimation of the annual energy production. The wind climate data are introduced in the model using a matrix representation, which defines the probability of occurrence of each combination of wind speed and propagation direction. The wind data input for the West of Barra site, considered in the analyses, is shown in the Fig. 5. Wind data are binned with respect to wind velocity magnitude and direction using the following discretization scheme:

wind speed interval: [2 m/s, 38 m/s] with 2 m/s bin width;

wind direction interval: [-180°, 180°] with 8° bin width.

Figure 5. Joint occurrence probability distribution of binned wind velocity and direction. “West of Barra” site (from ERA5 data).

The color bar in the figure above shows the probability of occurrence of each velocity and direction bin, both affecting the estimation of the wake interactions. The direction here reported and used in the model is expressed in a trigonometric convention, where 0° indicates wind blowing from west to east and angles are measured in the counterclockwise direction (as opposite to the meteorological convention).

7.2 MACHINE PERFORMANCE DATA

The machine power performance data, needed to estimate the annual energy production, are represented by the FOWT power curve. In this study the power curve used for the energy production estimation has been determined from simulation data.

Moreover, to estimate the wake interactions in a farm, the thrust coefficient of the machine is also needed as a function of the operating wind speed. These data have also been retrieved from simulation results. Details on the derivation of the power performance data are given in the deliverables dedicated to the analyses of the two considered control techniques (D5.1 [7] and D5.2 [8]).

7.3 SIMPLIFIED PARAMETRIZATION OF FARM LAYOUT AND WAKE MODELLING

The configuration layout has also a fundamental influence on the energy production performance of a wind farm. To explore the influence of the wake interaction effects in the examined cases, a simplified layout is assumed in the model, as indicated also in deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. The schematic array geometry depicted in Fig. 6 has been assumed.

Figure 6. Assumed farm layout.

The lateral and longitudinal spacing of the array is assumed constant and equal to each other, and is expressed as a multiple, s , of the rotor diameter, D_t :

$$H = W = sD_t \quad (43)$$

For the two cases examined in previous deliverables the following choices has been considered:

- D5.1, AWC control: $s = 8$
- D5.2, AWM control: $s = 5$

The choice of a larger non-dimensional distance for the AWC case is motivated by the fact that no direct action aimed at wake effect mitigation are considered in this case, thus a larger spacing between the installed units has been deemed representative of a more realistic situation. On the other hand, for the AWM case, which is explicitly aimed at improving wake recovery, a smaller spacing between the turbines has been considered with the purpose of highlighting possible benefits of the introduced control technique.

7.4 ANNUAL ENERGY CALCULATION

The estimation of the annual energy production has been carried out using a simplified approach, consistent with the preliminary character of the study. A procedure for the calculation of the overall energy production has been implemented within the excel file implementing the cost model. The procedure has been presented in deliverable D5.1, it is just briefly recalled here for completeness. The steps for the estimation of the AEP are summarized in the schematic flow chart shown in Figure 7.

The procedure is similar to the one used in other software, also available in the public domain, such as [31]. However, significant simplifications have been assumed, particularly with respect to the estimation of partial wake superposition, which are neglected in the considered approach.

In order to check the limits of the calculations based on the assumed simplified approach, a comparison has been carried out between the AEP estimated with the present model and the results of the commercial software WAsP, widely diffused in the field of farm production analyses (the software has been used in cooperation with the University of Naples “*Vanvitelli*”). The basic energy yield calculation tool available in the WAsP code has been used for AEP estimation, assuming the PARK model [32] [33] for the definition of the wake interactions. The wake modelling adopted in WAsP is based on the assumption of a constant velocity deficit in the wake, predicted using the momentum-deficit theory and considering a linearly expanding wake diameter, defined by a wake expansion coefficient. The wake expansion coefficient has been assumed equal to $k_w = 0.05$ (as suggested in [34] for offshore applications). Moreover, the WAsP wake model also includes the effect of partial superpositions of the wake generated by the upwind turbines on the trailing installed units. A logarithmic boundary layer is assumed in the WAsP model, accounting for the terrain or water surface through a parameter measuring the surface roughness, z (here assumed equal to a very low value of 0.0001 m for sea surface). Different values can be found in literature for the above indicated parameters; in the present study the values suggested by the WAsP manual has been considered.

For the comparison to the model used in the present study, in particular, the annual energy production for the simple square layout has been estimated for a variable number of turbines, from 4 to 49 installed units. The comparison is reported in terms of the total annual energy production in Table 15 and the variation of the difference between the codes is also illustrated in Figure 8.

It can be noted that a maximum error of about 1.5% is observed. The proposed calculation scheme generally underestimates the expected production, at least for the considered reference code and for the assumed layout. These differences can be attributed partly to the difference in model implementation between the codes, partly to the approximations assumed in the proposed approach, particularly for the absence of the effect of partial wake superposition. The observed differences are relatively small, even if not negligible; however, these discrepancies are considered acceptable in view of the purpose of obtaining a simple preliminary estimation tool.

Figure 7. Procedure for AEP calculation.

Table 15. Validation of the farm energy production estimate.

			Assumed AEP calc. Model	Reference code	diff. (%) AEP calc - reference val.
n. rows	n. lines	n turbines	AEP w/o AWC	AEP w/o AWC	
			(MWh/year)		
1	1	1	54262	54772	-0.93%
2	2	4	212865	215866	-1.39%
3	3	9	473384	480456	-1.47%
4	4	16	833836	846144	-1.45%
5	5	25	1293449	1311873	-1.40%
6	6	36	1851906	1877160	-1.35%
7	7	49	2508995	2541559	-1.28%

Figure 8. Percentage difference between the farm AEP estimated with the current numerical model and WASP software as a function of the farm size.

8 OVERALL COST BREAKDOWN

Using the cost estimation model outlined in the previous sections and implemented through an excel file, the overall cost breakdown for the considered baseline configuration has been obtained and is reported in Table 16. Results for energy production estimation have already been presented in the previous deliverables D5.1 and D5.2, together with the related LCOE values.

Table 16 shows a summary of the obtained results for a single turbine unit. Figure 9 shows a condensed version of the cost breakdown, reporting the cost subtotals for each main subcomponent.

Table 16. Cost breakdown for a single turbine for the baseline case.

Subcomponent	Cost item CAPEX	Cost	Percent
Rotor	Blades cost	2 997 428.53 €	4.77%
	Hub cost	554 218.70 €	0.88%
	Pitch mechanisms and bearings costs	723 129.68 €	1.15%
	Spinner, nose cone cost	21 480.97 €	0.03%
Nacelle	Low speed shaft cost	56 431.14 €	0.09%
	Main bearings cost	482 028.10 €	0.77%
	Gearbox cost	2 433 068.55 €	3.87%
	Mechanical brake	29 696.69 €	0.05%
	Generator	970 290.54 €	1.54%
	Variable speed electronics cost	765 902.85 €	1.22%
	Yaw drive and bearing cost	476 817.81 €	0.76%
	Mainframe cost	422 606.82 €	0.67%
	Electrical connections costs	387 798.91 €	0.62%
	Hydraulic and cooling systems costs	179 130.56 €	0.28%
	Nacelle cover cost	167 613.30 €	0.27%
	Control, safety system cost	53 322.35 €	0.08%
	Tower	Tower cost	3 159 641.82 €
Substructure and moorings	Substructure cost (SPAR)	27 842 749.26 €	44.27%
	Chain Cost	3 220 863.45 €	5.12%
	Drag-embedded Anchor Cost	822 350.14 €	1.31%
Installation	Turbine installation Cost (SPAR)	4 487 195.24 €	7.14%
	Substructure installation Cost (SPAR)	2 362 462.49 €	3.76%
	Port and Staging Cost (SPAR)	697 299.51 €	1.11%
Electrical connection	Electrical interconnection Cost	850 695.23 €	1.35%
	Marinization	831 204.50 €	1.32%
	Contingency (SPAR)	5 717 247.46 €	9.09%
	Insurance during construction	497 047.51 €	0.79%
	Project development Cost	1 680 000.00 €	2.67%
Total		62 889 722.10 €	100.00%

Figure 9. Cost breakdown for a single turbine.

8.1 COMPARISON OF THE COST VARIATION FOR THE CONSIDERED CONTROL TECHNIQUES

In general, more details on loads, costs and LCOE estimation for the two considered control techniques are reported separately in the dedicated deliverables: D5.1 for AWC control and D5.2 for the AWM case. Here only a summary of the findings related to the two examined configurations is reported.

The above reported cost breakdown is related to the baseline configuration, without the novel control techniques developed in the FLOATECH project. As described in the previous deliverable D5.1, the AWC control technique did not show significant variations of the loading conditions and thus no significant variations in the costs have been observed as well. In the case of the AWM control technique (D5.2), on the other hand, some variations have been observed for some of the main component loads and costs considered in the analysis. Table 17 reports a comparison for the AWM case, showing the cost variations of most affected components.

**Table 17. Cost comparison for the AWM case
(cost variations for the mainly affected components)**

Mooring		
Baseline	Modified	Difference
4 043 214 €	3 946 050 €	-97 164 €
		-2.40%
Platform		
Baseline	Modified	Difference
27 842 749 €	27 868 856 €	26 106 €
		0.09%
Tower		
Baseline	Modified	Difference
3 159 642 €	3 658 177 €	498 535 €
		15.78%

In the present analysis, the tower cost showed a larger sensitivity to the modification of the control strategy. This result can be justified considering that the AWM technique was intended to improve the wake recovery by increasing the wake oscillation through blade pitch action during the below-rated operation regime. In turn, the increased blade oscillations induce an increased thrust variation affecting tower fatigue loading.

Blade sizing and the related costs did not show, at least in the limit of the present analysis, a significant variation for the introduction of the AWM control case. Smaller variations in blade fatigue loads were observed, while the extreme loadings were essentially not affected by the control, not allowing for a reduction of blade sizing and costs. AWM strategy, as already noted, is in fact used only in the normal operation regime, while maximum loads are mainly observed in extreme conditions.

The reduction of the mooring cost is mainly due the modification of the mooring lines following a preliminary optimization of the mooring system needed to adjust the floater response to the operation requirements of the AWM control strategy (details can be found in D5.2).

Platform cost showed a small variation, due to the fact that, in the considered model, only a small portion of the upper part of the floater is influenced by the load variations transferred from the tower base to the platform.

It has to be noted that the reported results are valid in the limit of the assumptions of the model (as described in D5.1 and D5.2). In particular, only simplified structural calculations has been considered and only a small number of simulations has been carried out, consistently with the preliminary character of the study.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL OBSERVATIONS

This document presents the structure of the cost and energy production estimation model, developed during FLOATECH's WP5. The model, aiming at defining a tool for the preliminary evaluation of the techno-economic performance of a FOWT, has been developed using the experience and information gathered during the cost analyses of the two novel control techniques proposed in the FLOATECH project, which were investigated in the Task 5.1 and 5.2 (as described in the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2). The model for cost estimation of the baseline configuration (without the novel control strategies) is based on expressions derived from literature, while the cost variations for the modified configurations (with the new control strategies implemented) are estimated using a simplified sizing procedure described in the previous deliverables, which take into account the effect of the possible variations of loading conditions due to the change of control implementation. The baseline cost model is parametrized with respect to the main geometrical characteristics (such as rotor radius, tower height, etc.) and operational parameters (such as rated power) of the considered turbine. The effect of changing the control is represented, on the other side, considering the variation of the loads acting on the main turbine components, estimated from a set of simulations carried out using QBlade (as also described in the dedicated deliverables). Moreover, for the analysis of the global farm energy production performance, a simple farm layout (with a square arrangement of the installed units) has been considered. The developed energy production model has been used to estimate the effects of the wake interactions for the assumed climate and layout with the different control schemes. The results of the cost and energy production models have been used to estimate the LCOE for each of the examined control techniques, separately reported in D5.1 for the AWC control and in D5.2 for the AWM control.

A few general observations are here reported with respect to the cost estimation model:

- in agreement with similar studies, it can be noted that one of the largest contributions to the overall cost is related to the substructure; it can also be observed that another significant cost item is represented by the installation cost;
- relatively large cost values can, in general, be observed; such result can be, at least partially, associated to the relatively high inflation level characterizing the considered reference period (2022).

With respect to the energy production estimation model, the following observations are also reported:

- to estimate the effects of wake interactions (of particular interest for the case of the wake mixing technology, but relevant in general for the evaluation of the farm production performance), a simplified model to estimate the wake velocity deficit has been defined. For each couple of wind turbines, the velocity deficit is estimated, in the baseline case, using an engineering model; for the modified configuration, where needed, as for example in the case of the wake mixing control, a possible reduction of wake velocity deficit can be introduced based on simulation results;

- a simplified layout has been assumed. However, it has to be noted that the choice of a simplified layout, although consistent with the objective of the study, has some limitations. In particular, the layout has not been optimized for the specific wind direction distribution, thus potentially resulting in a suboptimal annual energy production estimate. However, the objective of the study was related to the comparison of different solutions, more than to the optimization of the wind energy resource exploitation. In this respect, the choice of a simple layout is oriented to reduce the possible uncertainty related to a non-uniform turbine arrangement. Moreover, the assumed layout, despite its simplicity, is consistent with the general tendency of the offshore wind plants to have a relatively regular distribution of FOWT units.

In the limits described in the above reported observations, the model has shown the ability to give a preliminary estimation of the expected LCOE values, accounting for the possible effects of alternative control techniques. The cost model will be further developed in future research activities, for example allowing its integration in a general optimization framework in order to account also for the FOWT economic performance.

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